

Hexagonal two layers-photonic crystal fiber based on surface plasmon resonance with gold coating biosensor easy to fabricate

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Jun 4, 2022

Revised Jul 12, 2022

Accepted Aug 2, 2022

Keywords:

Finite element method

HT-PCF-SPR

Photonic crystal fiber

Refractive index

Sensors

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we investigate a hexagonal two-layer photonic crystal fiber based on surface plasmon resonance (HT-PCF-SPR) which is easy to fabricate as a sensor for detecting the refractive index of analytes. After performing numerical simulations using COMSOL multiphysics based on the finite element method (FEM), it was found that the HT-PCF-SPR could detect the analyte's refractive index in the range 1.34-1.37 RIU and in the wavelength range from 730 nm to 810 nm. The plasmonic material used in the design is gold with a thickness of 40 nm which is located outside the layer and in two opposite air holes in the core. The HT-PCF-SPR design has good performance in detecting analytes, it is found that the sensitivity in detecting analytes is 2,000 nm/RIU, meaning that every 1 RIU shift of analyte shifts the wavelength by 2000 nm. Meanwhile, the sensor resolution obtained from the design is 6.67×10^{-5} RIU, and it is found that the larger the air hole, the greater the confinement loss value.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years the need for biosensors is very high, both in detecting biological samples whose refractive index changes very small. Several ways have been reported to overcome this, using surface plasmon resonance (SPR) technology based on photonic crystal fiber (PCF) will be a good technique in detecting analyte samples [1], for various applications such as in the medical world [2], food safety [3], environment and biochemistry [4]. SPR sensors are widely used in glucose sensing [5], virus detection [6], gas sensing [7], blood type detection [8], environmental sensing [9], food quality measurement [10], telemedicine [11], sensing temperature [12]-[15] and antigen-antibody interactions and other biochemical applications [13].

The technology was first proposed by Ritchie *et al.* in 1950, then Kretschmann and Otto introduced that optical excitation has basically two ways, such as attenuated total reflection (ATR) in a prism-coupler-based structure and diffraction in a lattice in 1968 [14], [15]. Many researchers have used the SPR technique which is applied as a sensor. Furthermore, Nylander and Liedberg introduced the application of attenuated total reflection in the application of SPW in 1983. Prismcoupler-based structures are in large size and large mechanical arrangement process [16]. A remarkable expansion was created after the basic idea of photonic crystal fiber (PCF) was given by Yeh *et al.* in 1978 and discovered by 2D PCF by P. Russel *et al.* in 1992 [17]. So that the incorporation of PCF-based SPR techniques offers advantages that make with micro size and

good performance. PCF is a modern fiber that has air holes around the cladding and core [18], unlike other optical fibers which only consist of a core, cladding, coating, or Bragg lattice fiber [19]. PCF has air holes around the core which has many geometric structures reported, PCF is usually composed of fused silica material. However, recently many studies have reported using different materials such as using topas [20], Zeonex [21], SF2 [22], and BK7 glass [23]. Although from research it was reported that PCF with silica material was able to provide relatively high sensitivity, high effective material loss, and low confinement loss. However, PCF with SF2 material has a high confinement loss compared to fused silica [22]. PCF in analyte sensing is usually combined with plasmonic materials to give rise to SPR phenomena such as gold [24], silver [25], titanium oxide (TiO₂) [26], silicon nitride (Si₃N₄) [27], aluminum [28], copper [29], and indium tin oxide (ITO) [30]. PCF-based SPR sensors have advantages over other sensors such as lightweight, microstructure [31], and wide sensing range [32]. Due to the presence of polarized light, the evanescent poles collide with the plasmonic material, creating surface plasmon waves (SPW). SPW depends on the refractive index of the surrounding medium (RI) which depends on the wavelength. For certain RI conditions, the maximum energy of the surface mode polariton (SPP) is transferred, this event is called resonance. So that PCF-based SPR has a fast and good response in detecting analytes [1].

Several studies related to PCF-SPR have been reported, some of which have complex structures and geometries that are difficult to fabricate as reported by Yang *et al.* PCF-SPR has a concave geometric structure that has low confinement loss values and wavelength sensitivity (WS). High that is 10,700 nm/RIU [33], the H-shaped PCF-SPR was also reported by Han *et al.* and it was found that the sensor sensing range was very large and the WS was obtained at 25,900 nm/RIU [34], further research conducted by Sakib demonstrated the PCF-SPR is in the form of a slot circuit and it is found that the WS is 16,000 nm/RIU [35]. Rahman *et al.* reported a PCF-SPR with a gold layer surrounding the microchannels having a WS of 25,000 nm/RIU [36]. Shayma *et al.* also investigated PCF-SPR in the form of a Mercedes Benz logo and obtained a WS of 700 nm/RIU [37]. However, most of the PCF-SPR recommended by many researchers have weaknesses in terms of fabrication, and a narrow sensing range that will make the fabrication cost expensive. PCF-SPR which has a simple structure has good performance and is easy to fabricate will make PCF-SPR a sophisticated technology that is effective in exploiting its advantages for detecting analytes. In this paper, we propose Hexagonal two layers of Photonics crystal fiber based on surface plasmon resonance (HT-PCF-SPR) with a simple geometric structure and easy fabrication, HT-PCF-SPR also has good performance in detecting analytes within a certain refractive index range, and good sensor resolution.

2. METHOD AND SENSOR GEOMETRY STRUCTURE

The design of the proposed PCF-SPR can be seen in Figure 1. The PCF-SPR has a hexagonal two-layer structure covered by gold plasmonic material, with a thickness of 40 nm. The gold layer is attached to the outside of the cladding and is also plated to the two air holes inside the core to give rise to the SPR phenomenon. In the PCF-SPR design, the holes have a tiered size, and the hole size getting to the center of the PCF has a smaller size. The hole sizes are d1 and d3 with different hole sizes and the distance between holes is d2. This paper also investigates the effect of the size of the air hole on the confinement loss value of the resulting material. The material used in this design is fused silica which can be defined in (1). Geometric structure of air holes and gold material HT-PCF-SPR As shown in Figure 1, size d1=0.46 μm, d2=1.8 μm, d3=0.35 μm and d4=0.4275 μm, meanwhile the thickness of gold is 40 nm. The method used in developing the HT-PCF-SPR is the finite element method (FEM) method with the help of COMSOL Multiphysics 5.6 software. The gold material used is defined as in (2). The analyte sensing system is carried out with an external sensing scheme.

Figure 1. The geometrical structure of the proposed HT-PCF-SPR

Figure 1 shows the proposed geometric structure, the geometric structure of PCF-SPR is hexagonal 2 layers, with a hole size approaching the core having a diameter of d_1 and hole size in the outermost layer having a diameter of d_2 . The distance between the holes is d_2 . Furthermore, the plasmonic material coats the two holes in the cladding and coats the core structure of the PCF clad. The size of the plasmonic material is 40 nm. The PCF material used in this study is fused silica. The analyte sensing layer is after the gold layer or also known as external sensing. At the end of the layer, a PML boundary layer with a width of $0.70125 \mu\text{m}$ was applied. Each air hole is arranged at an angle of 30° , 90° , and 150° for the first layer so as to form a hexagonal structure. The same is also done for the second layer of HT-PCF but with a larger air hole size compared to the first layer. Furthermore, in COMSOL the sensing wavelength is set at 750 nm. So that the cross-section is obtained as shown in Figure 2.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this paper, we investigate the hexagonal two-layer (HT-PCF-SPR) PCF-SPR design using the finite element method (FEM) using COMSOL Multiphysics 5.6. The PCF is covered by gold plasmonic material in the cladding and two holes in the core. In this investigation, PCF uses fused silica which can be defined by the sellmeier equation as in (1). Fused silica is a PCF material that is often used, and is reported to have the best performance when compared to other materials such as TOPAS, and Zeonex. The sellmeier equation can be used in defining the fused silica material in the HT-PCF-SPR design. The distribution of the refractive index for silica materials can be seen in (1) [35].

$$n(\lambda) = \sqrt{1 + \frac{0.696\lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - 0.0047} + \frac{0.408\lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - 0.014} + \frac{0.897\lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - 97.934}} \quad (1)$$

Where n is the refractive index of silica for each particular wavelength, λ is the wavelength used in PCF-SPR. The plasmonic material used to elicit the SPR effect on the PCF, the plasmonic material used in this study is gold, gold is chemically more stable than the environment but shows a wide resonance peak and this will harm the components. The drude-Lorentz model is used in calculating the dielectric constant of gold which can be shown in (2) [38].

$$\epsilon_{au} = \epsilon_\infty - \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega(\omega + j\gamma_D)} - \frac{\Delta\epsilon\Omega_L^2}{(\omega^2 - \Omega_L^2) + j\Gamma_L\omega} \quad (2)$$

With Au being the gold permittivity value, and high-frequency permittivity with a value of 5.9673, then ω is the plasma frequency, where ω_D is the dumping frequency and γ_D is the plasmon frequency which numerically has a value of 31.84π THz and 4227.2π THz and the oscillator power with symbol $L = 1300.14\pi$ THz, and the spectral width is $L = 209.72\pi$ THz. PCF that has air holes around the surface will cause loss when I pass through the surface. Confinement loss can be defined as (3) [35].

$$L_c(\text{dB/cm}) = \left(\frac{4\pi f}{c}\right) \text{Im}(n_{eff}) \times 10^4 \quad (3)$$

Where L_c is the material confinement loss, with a value of 3.14, f = frequency, n_{eff} is the effective refractive index, and c is the speed of light. Meanwhile, wavelength sensitivity can be defined in (4).

$$S_\lambda(\text{nm/RIU}) = \frac{\Delta\lambda_{peak}}{\Delta n} \quad (4)$$

Wavelength sensitivity shows how big the shift in the wavelength of the peak loss is for each change in the analyte's refractive index. A large shift for a small change in the refractive index of the analyte will show components that are ultra-sensitive and have high performance in differentiating changes in the refractive index of the analyte. Wavelength sensitivity also shows the difference in peak loss at a certain wavelength divided by the difference in the sensing refractive index. Furthermore, the sensor resolution is mathematically shown by (5) [34].

$$R = \frac{\Delta n_a \times \Delta\lambda_{min}}{\Delta\lambda_{peak}} \quad (5)$$

3.1. Cross-section HT-PCF-SPR

After numerical simulation, the cross-section of HT-PCF-SPR is obtained which is designed as shown in Figure 2. Gold plasmonic material coated in PCF-SPR cladding with a thickness of 40 nm gives rise to the SPR phenomenon as shown in Figure 2(a). Meanwhile, the polarization on the x-axis is shown in Figure 2(b) and the polarization of light on the nucleus that leads to the y-axis is shown in Figure 2(c).

Figure 2. The proposed PCF-SPR cross-section (a) surface plasmon mode, (b) x-polarization, and (c) y-polarization

The cross-section of PCF-SPR is shown in Figure 3. The polarization of light on the x-axis and y-axis is shown. Polarized light around the PCF-SPR surface with a cross-section as shown in Figure 3. This y-axis polarization is then explored to find the effective refractive index for each change in the analyte's refractive index on the component. So, from the imaginary value of the effective refractive index of each analyte for a certain wavelength, it can be found the confinement loss value of the material. The real refractive index and material confinement loss values in this design can be shown in Figure 3. It was found that the analyte refractive index of 1.35 RIU has the largest confinement loss peak. Figure 2(a) shows the cross-section surface plasmonic resonance component.

Figure 3. Cross section of HT-PCF-SPR with a thickness of Au 40 nm

3.2. Performance analysis for analytical detection

Furthermore, an analysis is carried out for each PCF-SPR hole distance to obtain the confinement loss shift in Figure 4. The farther the hole distance, the greater the confinement loss. It was found that the Hexagonal two-layer PCF-SPR can detect analytes in the range of 1.34 to 1.37 RIU as obtained in the figure below. The sensitivity of the hexagonal two layers PCF-SPR is 2,000 nm/RIU, every change of 1 RIU experiences a shift in the peak wavelength loss of 2,000 nm. These results show good sensitivity to detect analytes. HT-PCS-SPR can detect analytes with a refractive index of 1.34 to 1.37 RIU in the wavelength range of 730 nm to 810 nm. While the sensor resolution obtained is 6.67×10^{-5} . It is also found that the full width half maximum (FWHM) of the loss is 20 nm. The FWHM measure also shows that the sensor component has high accuracy in detecting the analyte. With the simple structure of HT-PCF-SPR and also showing good performance in detecting analytes, the design of this component can be applied to the biological or biochemical field to detect analytes, or can also be applied to detect healthy cells analytes and cancer cell analytes.

Figure 4. The shift of the confinement loss peak for each different wavelength

3.3. Performance analysis for different hole size distances

Next, the air hole size was analyzed from HT-PCF-SPR, this analysis was shown on hole sizes d_1 and d_3 in the range of $0.41 \mu\text{m}$ – $0.46 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.3 \mu\text{m}$ – $0.35 \mu\text{m}$, respectively, as shown in Figure 5. The refractive index of the analyte is made the same in this case, namely 1.34 RIU and the peak wavelength of confinement loss is 750 nm. It was found that the larger the size of the air hole in the HT-PCF-SPR design will also give the greater confinement loss of material, it is shown that at a wavelength of 750 nm, the HT-PCF-SPR with sizes d_1 and d_3 are $0.41 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.3 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. The confinement loss sensor is 191.1 dB/cm, then for sizes, d_1 and d_3 are $0.42 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.31 \mu\text{m}$, the confinement loss value is 192.1 dB/cm, there is an increase in confinement loss by 1 dB/cm, and so on, the confinement loss value increases with size. the air hole increases. The biggest loss confinement in size 1 is the value of d_1 and d_3 respectively $0.46 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.35 \mu\text{m}$ with a value of further the influence of the size of the air hole on the confinement loss value can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Analysis of HT-PCF-SPR performance on air hole size at 1.35 analyte refractive index

Figure 6. Effect of hole size on component confinement loss

Hole sizes 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6 are each the same variable value according to Figure 5. Figure 6 shows that the larger the air hole in the sensor component gives a larger confinement loss value, and it is obtained that HT-PCF-SPR can detect analytes in the range 1.34–1.37 RIU. This analyte range is evidenced by the presence of polarization to determine the imaginary effective refractive index that will be needed in determining the loss value, this is in accordance with (3). Figure 6 gives an almost linear value between hole size and material loss. Air hole 6 is the size of the largest hole diameter and also shows the most loss value, which is 200.4 dB/cm.

3.4. PCF-SPR performance analysis based on Distance between holes

Furthermore, the effect of the distance between holes was investigated with the loss that occurred in HT-PCF-SPR, in this case, the hole distance was varied by 1.8 μm, 1.9 μm, and 2 μm. This variation is taken to determine how much influence the size of the air hole has on material loss. It can be seen that the smaller the PCF-SPR hole distance, the smaller the component loss value in that range. These results indicate that the HT-PCF-SPR component will have a fairly large material loss value when compared to the components that have been proposed by other researchers. At a wavelength of 770 nm, HT-PCF-SPR with a hole distance of 1.8 μm has a confinement loss value of 227.88 dB/cm, while if the hole distance is increased to 1.9 μm the loss produced by HT-PCF-SPR is only 171.8 dB/cm then when raised to 2 μm the confinement loss is very small, only 130.78 dB/cm. Meanwhile, at a wavelength of 780 nm, all confinement loss values for air hole distances increased, respectively, approaching 104 dB/cm, 88 dB/cm, and 50 dB/cm. so these results indicate that when the HT-PCF-SPR component is fabricated with a 3-dimensional size, each increase in the length of the component will experience a different increase in a loss at a certain air hole distance. This result shows that the peak value of confinement loss occurs at a wavelength of 790 nm, after reaching that wavelength the value of each confinement loss also decreases as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Distribution of HT-PCF-SPR confinement loss value to air hole distance

In Figure 7, the effect of the air hole distance on the confinement loss value is investigated for the same hole size, the difference being the distance between one hole and another. This will also result in the diameter size of the resulting HT-PCF-SPR having a large dimension, getting bigger when the air hole distance is also large. Meanwhile, the gold layer is defined the same for each component, namely 40 nm.

4. CONCLUSION

The HT-PCF-SPR sensor was investigated for different polarization modes as core, cladding, and spp. The plasmonic material used in this paper is gold with a thickness of 40 nm. The HT-PCF-SPR component was designed using the finite element method (FEM) assisted by COMSOL Multiphysics software. The design results found that the HT-PCF-SPR can detect the refractive index in the range of 1.34–1.37 RIU and operate in the wavelength range of 730 nm–810 nm. It was found that the confinement loss component was getting bigger as the air hole size was getting bigger. In detecting the HT-PCF-SPR analyte, which has a sensitivity of 2,000 nm/RIU, the sensor resolution was found to be 6.67×10^{-5} RIU. The sensor component is recommended for sensing in the biological and biochemical fields because it has high sensitivity, and good resolution and the HT-PCF-SPR geometry is simple and easy to fabricate.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank LPPM Universitas Riau for their great support in this research under DRTPM Desentralisasi with contract no. 1643/UN19.5.1.3/PT.01.03/2022. We also would like to thank the head of the Optoelectronic Laboratory at the University of Riau and the BRIN Physics Research Center for facilitating research activities.

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